

Impact of Usage of Social Networking and Anxiety among PG Students of Central University of Punjab

*Ishfaq Majid**

Abstract

The present study was conducted to explore the influence of Usage of Social Networking Sites and Anxiety among PG students of Central University of Punjab. The objectives of the study were to analyze the usage of Social Networking Sites and Anxiety, finding out relationship between usage of SNS and Anxiety and comparing the usage of SNS between male, female, Science, Humanities PG Students of Central University of Punjab. The total number of 200 students were selected by using stratified random sampling technique for the collection of data. Data were collected by using Self-made questionnaire and Anxiety Scale by Pallavi Bhatnagar, Megha Singh, Manoj Pandey, Sandhya and Amitabh (2015). The study found that the maximum number of PG Students of Central University of Punjab comes under moderate level of usage of Social Networking Sites and Anxiety. The findings reveal that there is significant positive influence of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Anxiety among male PG students of Central University of Punjab. However, there is no influence of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Anxiety among female PG students of Central University of Punjab. The study also reveals that there is no impact of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Anxiety among PG students of Humanities. It was also found that there is no impact of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Anxiety among PG students of Science stream students and there is no significant difference in the usage of Social Networking Sites among PG students of Science and Humanities streams.

Keywords: Social Networking Sites, Anxiety, University Students

Introduction

The 21st century is the world of technology where most people do not even imagine their life without technology. Modern communication technology has undoubtedly transformed the whole world into a "global community". It helps people learn better, have an open mind and stay informed with global growth. Technology reveals to humanity a better way of doing things. Even today, beginning with the alarm on the phone and ends with the application messages on the smartphone. This situation also prevails in most of the rural areas. The use of technology in the classroom has two sides, as well as coins, both positive and negative. Most schools place more emphasis on computer education and the use of mobile learning because the use of this technology in today's classroom helps students to participate and learn actively to the needs of the students and receive feedback from an expert teacher. But most schools do not allow their students to use mobile devices because they think that by using this type of technology, students become technology-dependent and take less participation in face-to-face interaction with parents, teachers and colleagues who play a crucial role in improving social skills. Bandura in his social learning theory gives primary importance to observation. According to Bandura's theory, children learn by observing their classmates, teachers and parents. For example,

Research Scholar, School of Education, Central University of Gujarat.
Sector 29, Gandhinagar Gujarat. 382030 | Email: Panditishfaq786@gmail.com | Contact No.: 7006189324

children start walking as when the father walks because they observe them. Bandura emphasis on social skills that can be acquired by interacting with society in today's age. We discover that young students always interact with their technological toys, even most of the traffic accident is due to the use of the mobile phone during their journey.

Social Networking Sites

Social networking sites refer to various applications, websites or new online media that allows large numbers of individuals to share their information and develop a proper social and specialized contact. The various social networking sites are Facebook, LinkedIn, Instagram, snapshot, Youtube etc. Social networking sites (SNS) are online services that emphasize the creation of a connection between people to enable them to share their interests. These network sites allow people to share their information. Therefore, the main purpose of social networking sites is to allow people to share their real-life interests, activities and experiences.

Social networks refer mainly to the means used for interaction, which have become phenomena of growth in the social and academic field. Social media allows people and organizations to create, participate and share new or existing content through multi-way communication. Commonly, the phrase "social network sites" is used as a general term for all social networks, including Facebook, Twitter and Myspace. Over the past decade, every social networking application has worked collaboratively to provide a completely new multimedia experience that can now be accessed via mobile devices. In a related study, Brissette (2002) found that university students of both sexes completed measures of perceived stress, depression, network of friendship and social perception. Vitak (2008) reported in a study that there are several reasons why people use a social networking site. One of the reasons is that they meet strangers and become friends. Through social networking sites, users can keep their interpersonal relationship with their friends and users can send private messages and can use chat rooms as a method of communication. Lack et. al. (2009) reported in a study that most of the students who use social networking sites can easily access other user profiles by using their account information. He further says that formal education should be given over to students regarding the use of these sites. In a study, Petteet. al. (2009) reported that peoples and college student's uses social networking sites by several motivational reasons. Moreover the study has made several attempts to understand the choice, use, dispersal, adoption and acceptance of social networking sites among university students. Banquilet. al. (2009) reported in a study that "Social networking sites negatively impacting academic performance" and also indicated that friendship networks often require access to information and knowledge directly and indirectly and the effect of friendship on the academic performance of the students was confirmed. In a related study Anne et. al. (2009) reported that social networking sites significantly influence the educational performance of university students. Bicen and Cavus (2010) reported in their study that the use and exchange of knowledge on the internet is an integral or internal part of the life of university students. The findings of the study also reveal that Live Spaces and Facebook are the sites commonly used by students. Miller et. al. (2010) conducted a survey among students on the use of social networking sites and the capability of published content. The answers indicate that students regularly publish inappropriate content for all types of audiences, especially for potential employers. Park (2010) reported in his study that students used the profile service more than the community service while graduates used the community service plus the profile service. However, most of the faculty members were not active users of social media. Alabama. (2010) reported in his study that students are much more likely to use Facebook and are significantly more open to the possibility of using Facebook and similar

technologies to support work in the classroom than teachers. Teachers are more likely to use more "traditional" technologies such as e-mail. Das and Sahoo (2010) reported in their study that people use SNS for many purposes mainly because SNS offers the opportunity to express their points of view and provide independence and connect them with millions of people in the world. Kuppuswamy and Narayan (2010) reported the impact of social networking sites on the education of youth and found that social networking websites have both positive as well as negative impact on the education of youth, depending on their usage. Lin & Lu (2011) reported that enjoyment was the most influential factor for usage of growing social networking sites among college students. Hampton et. al. (2011) reported that social networks quickly gained popularity among their users and have now become an integral part of the lives of most of their users.

Anxiety

Anxiety is an emotion that predates the evolution of man. Its presence in human beings in a range of anxiety disorders makes it a vital clinical focus. Developments in nosology, epidemiology and psychobiology have significantly advanced our understanding of the anxiety disorders in recent years. Anxiety disorders involve a state of disturbing chronic but changeable nervousness that is inappropriately severe for the person's circumstances. The term anxiety has its origin from the Latin word "anxietas" which means to block regulate and upset emotional and psychological feature responses to the perception of danger. Anxiety could be a typical human feeling. Anxiety arises on preceding and adaptational response to difficult or nerve-wracking events. Anxiety is considered excessive or pathological once it arises within the absence of challenge or stress. Rosenquist et. al. (2011) reported that depression and anxiety may be involved in determining the size and structure of an individual's social network. Nimaet. al. (2013) conducted a study on "Anxiety, Affectivity, Self-Esteem & Stress and found that low self-esteem is associated with the pathogenesis of numerous mental illnesses, such as depression, eating disorders and addiction. McCord et. al. (2014) conducted a study on Facebook and anxiety which showed that the frequency of social use of Facebook does not predict social anxiety in the entire sample but is positively correlated with the anxiety. Seabrook (2016) conducted a study on social networking, depression and anxiety sites and found that positive interactions, social support and social connection in the SNS were coherently correlated with lower levels of depression and anxiety, while interaction and social comparisons in SNS were associated with higher levels of depression and anxiety.

Rationale of the study

Social Networking Sites (SNS) has become a subject of importance. It marked the shift of producer-generated content towards user-generated content. In the context of technology-enhanced learning, this paradigm change marks the shift from class e-learning, based on courses and the sequential presentation of learning material, towards more active participation of the learners and the support of the learners as a community of interest. On the basis of reviews, the investigator found that Social Networking Sites are Web-based platforms on which individuals connect with other users to generate and maintain social connections. Some studies reveal that users use Social Networking Sites for enjoyment. But some reviews show that the use of SNSs may lead to anxiety. On one hand, SNSs may protect from mental illness, as they support and enable social interaction and allow users to reflect aspects of their identity and express emotion that may be relevant to their life experience. On the other hand, there are many opportunities for miscommunications and mismanaged expectations and maladaptive tendencies can be exaggerated, leaving individuals feeling in a greater sense of isolation. Central University of Punjab (CUPB) is a university where students from all over the country come

for their future studies. Almost all the students of Central University of Punjab are using Social Networking Sites despite ban by the Universities authorities. Still students use Social Networking Sites by using Virtual Private Networks revealing the addiction of students towards Social Media. Hence the investigator got an opportunity to explore the influence of Social Networking Sites and Anxiety on the students of Central University of Punjab. So, the focus of my research will be how the usage of Social Networking Sites leads to anxiety among the Post Graduate students of Central University of Punjab.

Objectives

- To study the level of usage of Social Networking Sites among PG Students of Central University of Punjab
- To examine the level of Anxiety among PG Students of Central University of Punjab
- To explore the influence of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Anxiety among Male PG Students of Central University of Punjab
- To explore the influence of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Anxiety among Female PG Students of Central University of Punjab
- To study the impact of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Anxiety among PG Students of Humanities Stream of Central University of Punjab
- To study the impact of usage of Social Networking Sites on Anxiety among PG Students of Science stream of Central University of Punjab
- To compare the usage of Social Networking Sites of male and female PG students of Central University of Punjab.
- To compare the usage of Social Networking Sites among PG students of Science and Humanities streams of Central University of Punjab.
- To compare the level of Anxiety among PG students of Science and Humanities stream of Central University of Punjab
- To compare the level of Anxiety among male and female PG students of Central University of Punjab

Hypotheses

The study under investigation has the following hypotheses;

- Majority of PG Students of Central University of Punjab will come under higher level of usage of Social Networking Sites
- Majority of PG Students of Central University of Punjab will depict low level of Anxiety.
- There will be no significant influence of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Anxiety among Male PG Students of Central University of Punjab
- There will be no significant influence of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Anxiety among Female PG Students of Central University of Punjab
- Usage of Social Networking Sites will put no significant impact on Anxiety among PG Students of Humanities Stream of Central University of Punjab

- Usage of Social Networking Sites will put no significant impact on Anxiety among PG Students of Science stream of Central University of Punjab
- There will be no significant difference in the usage of Social Networking Sites among the male and female PG students of Central University of Punjab.
- There will be no significant difference in the usage of Social Networking Sites among PG students of Science and Humanities streams of Central University of Punjab.

Method

In the present study, the researcher used the descriptive method of research. In the present study, Social Networking Sites is an independent variable while as Anxiety is Dependent variable. In the present study, a sample of 200 postgraduate students were taken and then classified according to their flows. The sample was further divided into gender-wise and stream-wise. Statistical techniques Percentage Analysis, Correlation and t-test were used for testing the hypotheses. For the present study, the researcher used the stratified random sampling technique for the purpose of collection of data. Data were collected from the PG students of Central Punjab University, Bathinda. Hence all the PG students of Central University of Punjab constituted as the population of the study.

Tools

For the present study, the following tools were used

- Anxiety scale (2011) by Pallavi Bhatnagar, Megha Singh, Manoj Pandey, Sandhya and Amitabh.
- Self-made Questionnaire on checking Usage of Social Networking Sites was developed by the investigator.

Results

- Table 1.1 reveals the level of Social Networking Sites among PG students of Central University of Punjab. It was revealed that out of 200 students, 18% of the PG students fall under higher level of Usage of Social Networking Sites, 68% fall in the moderate level and 14% fall in the Low level of Usage of Social Networking Sites. It was found that majority of the PG students of Central University of Punjab have moderate level of Usage of Social Networking Sites. Hence the hypothesis is rejected.

Usage of SNS	N	High Level of Usage of SNS	Moderate Level of Usage of SNS	Low Level of Usage of SNS
	200	18%	68%	14%

Table 1.1: Level of Usage of Social Networking Sites

- Table 1.2 reveals the level of level of Anxiety among PG students of Central University of Punjab. It was revealed that out of 200 students, 16% of PG students fall under normal level of Anxiety, 8.5% fall under mild level, 38.5% fall under moderate level & 37% fall under

severe level of Anxiety. it was found that maximum number of the PG students of Central University of Punjab have moderate level of Anxiety. Hence the hypothesis is rejected.

Table 1.2: Level of Anxiety

Level of Anxiety	N	Normal level of Anxiety	Mild level of Anxiety	Moderate level of Anxiety	Severe level of Anxiety
	200	16%	8.5%	38.5%	37%

- Table 1.3 shows the coefficient of correlation between Usage of Social Networking Sites and Anxiety among male PG students of Central University of Punjab. It was revealed from table 1.3 that the r-value of Usage of Social Networking Sites and Anxiety of male students of Central University of Punjab is 0.0175 which is less than table value of r with the df of 200 at 0.05 i.e. 198. Hence r-value is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence it can be interpreted that from the table 1.2 that the coefficient of correlation is positive, so there is a significant positive influence of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Anxiety among male PG students of Central University of Punjab. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 1.3: Coefficient of Correlation between Usage of Social Networking Sites and Anxiety among male PG students of Central University of Punjab

Variables	N	Df	'r' value	Level of significance	Remark
Usage of SNS	100	198	0.0175	< 0.05	Positive correlation
Anxiety	100				

- Table 1.4 shows the coefficient of correlation between Usage of Social Networking Sites and Anxiety among female PG students of Central University of Punjab. It was revealed from table 3.3 that the r-value of Usage of Social Networking Sites and Anxiety of female students of Central University of Punjab is -0.01235 which is less than table value of r with the df of 200 at 0.05 i.e. 198. Hence r-value is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence it can be interpreted that from the table 3.3 the coefficient of correlation is negative, so there is a no influence of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Anxiety among female PG students of Central University of Punjab. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Table 1.4: Coefficient of Correlation between Usage of Social Networking Sites and Anxiety among female PG students of Central University of Punjab

Variables	N	df	'r' value	Level of Significance	Remarks
Usage of SNS	100	198	-0.1235	< 0.05	Negative Correlation
Anxiety	100				

- Table 1.5 shows the coefficient of correlation between Usage of Social Networking Sites and Anxiety among PG students of Humanities Stream of Central University of Punjab. It was revealed from table 1.5 that the r-value of Usage of Social Networking Sites and Anxiety of PG students of Humanities stream of CUPB is -0.0382 which is less than table value of r with the df of 200 at 0.05 i.e. 198. Hence r-value is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence it can be interpreted that the coefficient of correlation is negative, so there is a no impact of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Anxiety among PG students of Humanities stream students of CUPB. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 1.5: Coefficient of Correlation between Usage of Social Networking Sites and Anxiety among PG Students of Humanities Stream of CUPB

Variables	N	df	'r' value	Level of Significance	Remarks
Usage of SNS	100	198	-0.0382	< 0.05	Negative Correlation
Anxiety	100				

- Table 1.6 shows the coefficient of correlation between Usage of Social Networking Sites and Anxiety among PG students of Science Stream of Central University of Punjab. It was revealed from table 1.6 that the r-value of Usage of Social Networking Sites and Anxiety of PG students of Science stream of CUPB is -0.0648 which is less than table value of r with the df of 200 at 0.05 i.e. 198. Hence r-value is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence it can be interpreted that from the table 3.5 the coefficient of correlation is negative, so there is a no impact of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Anxiety among PG students of Science stream students of CUPB. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 1.6: Coefficient of Correlation between Usage of Social Networking Sites and Anxiety among PG Students of Science Stream of CUPB

Variables	N	df	'r' value	Level of Significance	Remarks
Usage of SNS	100	198	-0.0648	< 0.05	Negative Correlation
Anxiety	100				

The below table 1.7 shows the Mean, S.D, t- value and level of significance of usage of Social Networking Sites among male and female PG students of Central University of Punjab. From the

table it was revealed that the mean value of Usage of social networking sites of male and female are 86.88 and 86.78 respectively. The S.D. of male students is 7.67 and that of female students is 5.96. Also, the calculated t-value is 0.10 which is less than table value of t with the df 198 at 0.05 level i.e. 1.98. Hence, it is concluded that the t-value is not significant at 0.05 level. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted i.e. there is no significant difference between usage of Social Networking Sites among male and female PG students of Central University of Punjab.

Table 1.7: Comparison of usage of Social Networking Sites among the male and female PG students of Central University of Punjab

Variables	N	Mean	S.D.	't' value	Level of significance
Male	100	86.88	7.67	0.10	< 0.05
Female	100	86.78	5.96		

- The below table 1.8 shows the Mean, S.D, t- value and level of significance of usage of Social Networking Sites among PG students of Science and Humanities streams of Central University of Punjab. From the table, it was revealed that the mean value of Usage of social networking sites of Humanities and Science stream students are 87.56 and 86.1 respectively. The S.D. of Humanities student is 6.484 and that of Science students is 7.156. Also the calculated t-value is 1.50 which is less than table value of t with the df 198 at 0.05 level i.e. 1.98. Hence, it is concluded that the t-value is not significant at 0.05 level. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted i.e. there is no significant difference between usage of Social Networking Sites among science and Humanities PG students of Central University of Punjab.

Table 1.8: Comparison of usage of Social Networking Sites among PG students of Science and Humanities streams of CUPB

Variables	N	Mean	S.D.	df	't' value	Level of significance
Humanities	100	87.56	6.484	198	1.50	< 0.05
Science	100	86.1	7.156			

Discussion

- Majority of PG Students of Central University of Punjab comes under moderate level of usage of Social Networking Sites. The statistical data of the study reveal that 68% of the PG students of Central University of Punjab have moderate level of Usage of Social Networking Sites. However only 18% & 14% of the PG students comes under High & Low level of Usage of Social networking Sites respectively.
- Majority of PG Students of Central University of Punjab comes under moderate level of Anxiety. The statistical data shows that out of 200 students, 16% of PG students fall under Normal level, 8.5% students fall under Mild level, 38.5% fall under Moderate level & 37% fall under severe level of Anxiety.

- There is significant positive influence of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Anxiety among male PG students of Central University of Punjab. The findings of the study were supported by Ahmet and Murat (2017).
- There is no significant influence of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Anxiety among Female PG Students. The findings reveal that Usage of Social Networking Sites has negative effect on Anxiety among female PG students of Central University of Punjab because using Social Networking Sites cause Social anxiety, feelings of loneliness and problematic addiction which results in Anxiety among students.
- The Usage of Social Networking Sites has significant negative impact on Anxiety among PG Students of Humanities Stream.
- The Usage of Social Networking Sites has significant negative impact on Anxiety, among PG Students of Science stream. The findings reveal that Social Networking Sites have negative impact on Anxiety among PG Students of Science Stream of Central University of Punjab because using social networking sites is considered a risk factor for mental health problems and activities like cyber bullying leads to Anxiety among Science stream students.
- There is no significant difference in the usage of Social Networking Sites among the male and female PG students. Male students and the female students almost have same level of usage of Social Networking Sites.
- There is no significant difference in the usage of Social Networking Sites among PG students of Science and Humanities streams. Male students and the female students almost have same level of usage of Social Networking Sites.

Conclusion

The investigator is fully aware of the limitations under which the present research was conducted and therefore accepts that no broad conclusions could be made. These findings are only indicative of trends and hence following suggestions can be given for further research. The tools adopted for the present study was used as such without any modifications. The results of the study lack in external validity as the sample size was not large. The study was limited to post graduate students of Central University of Punjab.

Reference

- Brissette, I., Scheier, M. F. and Carver, C. S. (2002). The role of optimism in social network development, coping, and psychological adjustment during a life transition. *PubMed Central articles*, 82(1), 102-11. Retrieved from <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/11811628>
- Vitak, J. M. (2008). Facebook Friends: How Online identities Impact Offline Relations. *Washington, D.C.* Retrieved From <https://goo.gl/R4WdWd>.
- Lack, C. W., Beck, L. and Danielle, H. (2009). Use of Social Networking by Undergraduate Psychology Majors. *First Monday*, 14(12). Retrieved from <https://goo.gl/gRWgX6>.
- Banquil, K., Chua, N. A., Leano, G. A., Rivero, M. A., Burce, C. A., Dianalan, S. A., . . . Timog, N. U. (2009). Social networking sites affect tone's academic performance adversely. Retrieved from <https://goo.gl/a06stg>.

- Bicen, H. and Cavus, N. (2010). The Most Preferred Social Network Sites by Students. *Procedia Social and Behavioural Sciences*, 2(2), 5864-5869. doi: [10.1016/j.sbspro.2010.03.958](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2010.03.958).
- Miller, R., Parsons, K., and Lifer, D. (2010). Students and Social Networking Sites: The Posting Paradox. *Behaviour and Information Technology*, 29(4), 377-382. doi: [10.1080/01449290903042491](https://doi.org/10.1080/01449290903042491).
- Park J. (2010). Differences among University Students and Faculties in Social Networking Site Perception and Use: Implications for Academic Library Services. *The Electronic Library*, 28(3), 417-431. doi: [10.1108/02640471011051990](https://doi.org/10.1108/02640471011051990).
- Roblyer, M. D., McDaniel, M., Webb, M., Herman, J., Witty, J. V. (2010) Findings on Facebook in higher education: A comparison of college faculty and student uses and perceptions of social networking sites. *The Internet and Higher Education*. 13(3), 134-140. doi: [10.1016/j.iheduc.2010.03.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iheduc.2010.03.002).
- Das, D. B., Sahoo, J. S. (2011). Social Networking Sites – A Critical Analysis of Its Impact on Personal and Social Life. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 2(14), 222-228. Retrieved From <https://goo.gl/OguOvY>.
- Kuppuswamy, S., Narayan, P. B. S. (2010). The Impact of Social Networking Websites on the Education of Youth. *International Journal of Virtual Communities and Social Networking*, 2(1), 67-79. Retrieved From <https://goo.gl/Ule7aD>.
- Lin, K., Lu, H. P. (2011). Why People Use Social Networking Sites: An Empirical Study Integrating Network Externalities and Motivation Theory. *Computers in Human Behaviour*, 27(3), 1152-1161. doi: [10.1016/j.chb.2010.12.009](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2010.12.009).
- Hampton, K. N, Goulet, L.S., Rainie, L., Purcell K. (2011). Social Networking Sites and Our Lives. *Pew Research: Washington, D.C.* Retrieved From <https://goo.gl/NKsS0X>.
- Rosenquist, J.N., Fowler, J. H., Christakis, N.A. (2011). Social Network Determinants of Depression. *Molecular Psychiatry*, 16(3), 273–81. doi: [10.1038/mp.2010.13](https://doi.org/10.1038/mp.2010.13)
- Nima, A. A., Rosenberg, P. Archer, T. et al (2013). Anxiety, affect, self-esteem, and stress: mediation and moderation effects on depression. *Plos One*. doi: [10.1371/journal.pone.0073265](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0073265).
- McCord, B., Rodebaugh, T. L., Levinson, C. A. (2014) *Facebook: social uses and anxiety*. *Computers in Human Behaviour*. 34, 23–27. doi: [10.1016/j.chb.2014.01.020](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2014.01.020)
- Seabrook. M.E., Kern. L.M. and Rickard. S.N. (2016).** Social Networking Sites, Depression, and Anxiety: A Systematic Review. *JMIR Mental Health*. 3(4). Retrieved from doi: [10.2196/mental.5842](https://doi.org/10.2196/mental.5842)